

Versioned Archive and Review of Biotic
Interactions and Taxon Names Found within
globalbioticinteractions/spire
hash://md5/c06717f600688269e4be13a55fcdf7b3

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<https://github.com/globalbioticinteractions/spire/issues>

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Abstract

Life on Earth is sustained by complex interactions between organisms and their environment. These biotic interactions can be captured in datasets and published digitally. We present a review and archiving process for such an openly accessible digital interactions dataset of known origin and discuss its outcome. The dataset under review, named globalbioticinteractions/spire, has fingerprint hash://md5/c06717f600688269e4be13a55fcdf7b3, is 30.6MiB in size and contains 30,167 interactions with 1 unique type of association (e.g., eats) between 3,491 primary taxa (e.g., Actinopterygii) and 2,743 associated taxa (e.g., detritus). This report includes detailed summaries of interaction data, a taxonomic review from multiple catalogs, and an archived version of the dataset from which the reviews are derived.

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Introduction

Data Review and Archive

Data review and archiving can be a time-consuming process, especially when done manually. This review report aims to help facilitate both activities. It automates the archiving of datasets, including Darwin Core archives, and is a citable backup of a version of the dataset. Additionally, an automatic review of species interaction claims made in the dataset is generated and registered with Global Biotic Interactions (J. H. Poelen, Simons, and Mungall 2014).

This review includes summary statistics about, and observations about, the dataset under review :

Semantic Prototypes in Research Ecoinformatics (SPIRE). Data provided by Joel Sachs. See also <http://ebiquity.umbc.edu/get/a/publication/297.pdf>
. <https://github.com/globalbioticinteractions/spire/archive/b2f52536ed93797820e4295fe1097310d37ddb2026-01-31T05:16:00.171Z> hash://md5/c06717f600688269e4be13a55fcdf7b3

For additional metadata related to this dataset, please visit <https://github.com/globalbioticinteractions/spire> and inspect associated metadata files including, but not limited to, *README.md*, *eml.xml*, and/or *globi.json*.

Methods

The review is performed through programmatic scripts that leverage tools like Preston (Elliott et al. 2025), Elton (Kuhn, Poelen, and Leinweber 2025), Nomer (Salim and Poelen 2025), globinizer (J. Poelen, Seltmann, and Mietchen 2024) combined with third-party tools like `grep`, `mlr`, `tail` and `head`.

Table 1: Tools used in this review process

tool name	version
preston	0.11.1
elton	0.16.4
nomer	0.5.17
globinizer	0.4.0
mlr	6.0.0
jq	1.6
yq	4.25.3
pandoc	3.1.6.1
duckdb	1.3.1
mapserver	7.6.4

The review process can be described in the form of the script below ¹.

```
# get versioned copy of the dataset (size approx. 30.6MiB) under review
elton pull globalbioticinteractions/spire

# generate review notes
elton review globalbioticinteractions/spire\
> review.tsv

# export indexed interaction records
elton interactions globalbioticinteractions/spire\
> interactions.tsv

# export names and align them with the Catalogue of Life using Nomer
elton names globalbioticinteractions/spire\
| nomer append col\
> name-alignment.tsv
```

or visually, in a process diagram.

Figure 1: Review Process Overview

¹Note that you have to first get the data (e.g., via `elton pull globalbioticinteractions/spire`) before being able to generate reviews (e.g., `elton review globalbioticinteractions/spire`), extract interaction claims (e.g., `elton interactions globalbioticinteractions/spire`), or list taxonomic names (e.g., `elton names globalbioticinteractions/spire`)

You can find a copy of the full review script at `check-data.sh`. See also GitHub and Codeberg.

Results

In the following sections, the results of the review are summarized ². Then, links to the detailed review reports are provided.

Files

The following files are produced in this review:

filename	description
biblio.bib	list of bibliographic reference of this review
check-dataset.sh	data review workflow/process as expressed in a bash script
data.zip	a versioned archive of the data under review
HEAD	the digital signature of the data under review
index.docx	review in MS Word format
index.html	review in HTML format
index.md	review in Pandoc markdown format
index.pdf	review in PDF format
indexed-citations.csv.gz	list of distinct reference citations for reviewed species interaction claims in gzipped comma-separated values file format
indexed-citations.html.gz	list of distinct reference citations for reviewed species interactions claims in gzipped html file format
indexed-citations.tsv.gz	list of distinct reference citations for reviewed species interaction claims in gzipped tab-separated values format
indexed-interactions-col-family-col-family.svg	network diagram showing the taxon family to taxon family interaction claims in the dataset under review as interpreted by the Catalogue of Life via Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024)

²Disclaimer: The results in this review should be considered friendly, yet naive, notes from an unsophisticated robot. Please keep that in mind when considering the review results.

filename	description
indexed-interactions-col-kingdom-col-kingdom.svg	network diagram showing the taxon kingdom to taxon kingdom interaction claims in the dataset under review as interpreted by the Catalogue of Life via Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024)
indexed-interactions.csv.gz	species interaction claims indexed from the dataset under review in gzipped comma-separated values format
indexed-interactions.html.gz	species interaction claims indexed from the dataset under review in gzipped html format
indexed-interactions.tsv.gz	species interaction claims indexed from the dataset under review in gzipped tab-separated values format
indexed-interactions.parquet	species interaction claims indexed from the dataset under review in Apache Parquet format
indexed-interactions.png	species interaction claims indexed from the dataset under review plotted on a map
indexed-interactions.gpkg	species interaction claims indexed from the dataset under review in GeoPackage format
indexed-interactions-h3.gpkg	geospatially clustered h3 species interaction claims indexed from the dataset under review in GeoPackage format
indexed-interactions-sample.csv	list of species interaction claims indexed from the dataset under review in gzipped comma-separated values format
indexed-interactions-sample.html	first 500 species interaction claims indexed from the dataset under review in html format
indexed-interactions-sample.tsv	first 500 species interaction claims indexed from the dataset under review in tab-separated values format
indexed-names.csv.gz	taxonomic names indexed from the dataset under review in gzipped comma-separated values format
indexed-names.html.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review in gzipped html format

filename	description
indexed-names.tsv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review in gzipped tab-separated values format
indexed-names.parquet	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review in Apache Parquet format
indexed-names-resolved-col.csv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the Catalogue of Life as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped comma-separated values format
indexed-names-resolved-col.html.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the Catalogue of Life as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped html format
indexed-names-resolved-col.tsv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the Catalogue of Life as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped tab-separated values format
indexed-names-resolved-col.parquet	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the Catalogue of Life as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in Apache Parquet format
indexed-names-resolved-discoverlife.csv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with Discover Life bee species checklist as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped comma-separated values format

filename	description
indexed-names-resolved-discoverlife.html.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with Discover Life bee species checklist as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped html format
indexed-names-resolved-discoverlife.tsv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with Discover Life bee species checklist as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped tab-separated values format
indexed-names-resolved-discoverlife.parquet	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with Discover Life bee species checklist as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in Apache Parquet format
indexed-names-resolved-gbif.csv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with GBIF Backbone Taxonomy as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped comma-separated values format
indexed-names-resolved-gbif.html.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with GBIF Backbone Taxonomy as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped html format
indexed-names-resolved-gbif.tsv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with GBIF Backbone Taxonomy as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped tab-separated values format

filename	description
indexed-names-resolved-gbif.parquet	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with GBIF Backbone Taxonomy as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in Apache Parquet format
indexed-names-resolved-itis.csv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with Integrated Taxonomic Information System (ITIS) as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped comma-separated values format
indexed-names-resolved-itis.html.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with Integrated Taxonomic Information System (ITIS) as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped html format
indexed-names-resolved-itis.tsv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with Integrated Taxonomic Information System (ITIS) as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped tab-separated values format
indexed-names-resolved-itis.parquet	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with Integrated Taxonomic Information System (ITIS) as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in Apache Parquet format
indexed-names-resolved-mdd.csv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the Mammal Diversity Database as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped comma-separated values format

filename	description
indexed-names-resolved-mdd.html.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with Mammal Diversity Database as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped html format
indexed-names-resolved-mdd.tsv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with Mammal Diversity Database as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped tab-separated values format
indexed-names-resolved-mdd.parquet	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with Mammal Diversity Database as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in Apache Parquet format
indexed-names-resolved-ncbi.csv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the NCBI Taxonomy as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped comma-separated values format
indexed-names-resolved-ncbi.html.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the NCBI Taxonomy as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped html format
indexed-names-resolved-ncbi.tsv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the NCBI Taxonomy as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped tab-separated values format

filename	description
indexed-names-resolved-ncbi.parquet	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the NCBI Taxonomy as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in Apache Parquet format
indexed-names-resolved-pbdb.csv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the Paleobiology Database as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped comma-separated values format
indexed-names-resolved-pbdb.html.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with Paleobiology Database as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped html format
indexed-names-resolved-pbdb.tsv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with Paleobiology Database as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped tab-separated values format
indexed-names-resolved-pbdb.parquet	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with Paleobiology Database as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in Apache Parquet format
indexed-names-resolved-tpt.csv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the Terrestrial Parasite Tracker (TPT) Taxonomic Resource as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped comma-separated values format

filename	description
indexed-names-resolved-tpt.html.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the Terrestrial Parasite Tracker (TPT) Taxonomic Resource as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped html format
indexed-names-resolved-tpt.tsv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the Terrestrial Parasite Tracker (TPT) Taxonomic Resource as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped tab-separated values format
indexed-names-resolved-tpt.parquet	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the Terrestrial Parasite Tracker (TPT) Taxonomic Resource as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in Apache Parquet format
indexed-names-resolved-wfo.csv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the World of Flora Online as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped comma-separated values format
indexed-names-resolved-wfo.html.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the World of Flora Online as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped html format
indexed-names-resolved-wfo.tsv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the World of Flora Online as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped tab-separated values format

filename	description
indexed-names-resolved-wfo.parquet	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the World of Flora Online as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in Apache Parquet format
indexed-names-resolved-worms.csv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the World Register of Marine Species (WoRMS) as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped comma-separated values format
indexed-names-resolved-worms.html.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the World Register of Marine Species (WoRMS) as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped html format
indexed-names-resolved-worms.tsv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the World Register of Marine Species (WoRMS) as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped tab-separated values format
indexed-names-resolved-worms.parquet	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the World Register of Marine Species (WoRMS) as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in Apache Parquet format
indexed-names-sample.csv	first 500 taxonomic names found in the dataset under review in comma-separated values format
indexed-names-sample.html	first 500 taxonomic names found in the dataset under review in html format
indexed-names-sample.tsv	first 500 taxonomic names found in the dataset under review in tab-separated values format

filename	description
interaction.svg	diagram summarizing the data model used to index species interaction claims
nanopub-sample.trig	first 500 species interaction claims as expressed in the nanopub format (Kuhn and Dumontier 2014)
nanopub.trig.gz	species interaction claims as expressed in the nanopub format (Kuhn and Dumontier 2014)
process.svg	diagram summarizing the data review processing workflow
prov.nq	origin of the dataset under review as expressed in rdf/nquads
review.csv.gz	review notes associated with the dataset under review in gzipped comma-separated values format
review.html.gz	review notes associated with the dataset under review in gzipped html format
review.tsv.gz	review notes associated with the dataset under review in gzipped tab-separated values format
review-sample.csv	first 500 review notes associated with the dataset under review in comma-separated values format
review-sample.html	first 500 review notes associated with the dataset under review in html format
review-sample.tsv	first 500 review notes associated with the dataset under review in tab-separated values format
review.svg	a review badge generated as part of the dataset review process
zenodo.json	metadata of this review expressed in Zenodo record metadata

Archived Dataset

Note that *data.zip* file in this archive contains the complete, unmodified archived dataset under review.

Figure 2: Biotic Interaction Data Model

Biotic Interactions

In this review, biotic interactions (or biotic associations) are modeled as a primary (aka subject, source) organism interacting with an associate (aka object, target) organism. The dataset under review classified the primary/associate organisms with specific taxa. The primary and associate organisms The kind of interaction is documented as an interaction type.

The dataset under review, named `globalbioticinteractions/spire`, has fingerprint hash://md5/c06717f600688269e4be13a55fcd7b3, is 30.6MiB in size and contains 30,167 interactions with 1 unique type of association (e.g., eats) between 3,491 primary taxa (e.g., Actinopterygii) and 2,743 associated taxa (e.g., detritus).

An exhaustive list of indexed interaction claims can be found in gzipped csv, tsv, geopackage and parquet archives. To facilitate discovery, a preview of claims available in the gzipped html page at `indexed-interactions.html.gz` are shown below.

The exhaustive list was used to create the following data summaries below.

Table 3: Sample of Indexed Interaction Claims

sourceTaxonName	interactionTypeName	targetTaxonName	referenceCitation
Cephalopoda	eats	Engraulidae	Yodzis P (2000) Diffuse effects in food webs. Ecology 81:261-266

sourceTaxonName	interactionTypeName	targetTaxonName	referenceCitation
Syngnathus scovelli	eats	algae	Christian RR, Luczkovich JJ (1999) Organizing and understanding a winter's seagrass foodweb network through effective trophic levels. Ecol Model 117:99-124
invertebrates	eats	detritivorous invertebrates	T. Mizuno and J. I. Furtado, Food chain. In: Tasek Bera, J. I. Furtado and S. Mori, Eds. (Junk, The Hague, Netherlands, 1982), pp. 357-359, from p. 358.
Pycnocentroides	eats	Navicula rhynchocephala	Thompson, RM and Townsend, CR. 1999. The effect of seasonal variation on the community structure and food-web attributes of two streams: implications for food-web science. Oikos 87: 75-88.

Table 4: Most Frequently Mentioned Interaction Types (up to 20 most frequent)

interactionTypeName	count
eats	30167

Table 5: Most Frequently Mentioned Primary Taxa (up to 20 most frequent)

sourceTaxonName	count
Actinopterygii	454
Hydora nitida	387
Deleatidium	337
Austrosimulium australense	309
Oligochaeta II	307
Aoteapsyche	306
Salmo trutta	295
Aphrophila noevaezelandiae	284
Oligochaeta I	252
Potamopyrgus antipodarum	238
Coloburiscus humeralis	227
Tanytarsini	227
Homo sapiens	201
Helicopsyche albescens	180
Olinga feredayi	173
Austroclima jollyae	172
Perca flavescens	162
Pycnocentroides	161
Hudsonema amabilis	160

Table 6: Most Frequently Mentioned Associate Taxa (up to 20 most frequent)

targetTaxonName	count
detritus	1205
Insecta	445
Actinopterygii	319
Nitzschia	318
Fragilaria vaucheriae	293
Achnanthes lanceolata	288
Cocconeis	282
Cymbella minuta	278
Rhoicosphenia curvata	274
Synedra ulna	272
Tabellaria flocculosa	270
Navicula avenacea	268
Plant material	257
algae	251
phytoplankton	246

targetTaxonName	count
Cyclotella	245
Diatoma heimale	241
Gomphoneis herculeana	228
Achnanthes linearis	212

Table 7: Most Frequent Interactions between Primary and Associate Taxa (up to 20 most frequent)

sourceTaxonName	interactionTypeName	targetTaxonName	count
Actinopterygii	eats	Actinopterygii	67
zooplankton	eats	phytoplankton	25
Actinopterygii	eats	zooplankton	23
Actinopterygii	eats	Decapoda	22
Chondrichthyes	eats	Actinopterygii	21
Hydora nitida	eats	detritus	19
Scirtidae	eats	detritus	18
Actinopterygii	eats	phytoplankton	17
Aves	eats	Actinopterygii	17
Staphylinidae	eats	Fannia	16
Hydora nitida	eats	Nitzschia	16
Deleatidium	eats	detritus	16
Deleatidium	eats	Achnanthes lanceolata	16
Austrosimulium australe	eats	detritus	16
Oligochaeta II	eats	detritus	16
Hydora nitida	eats	Cymbella minuta	15
Deleatidium	eats	Nitzschia	15
Hydora nitida	eats	Cocconeis	15
Austrosimulium australe	eats	Nitzschia	15

Interaction Networks

The figures below provide a graph view on the dataset under review. The first shows a summary network on the kingdom level, and the second shows how interactions on the family level. It is important to note that both network graphs were first aligned taxonomically using the Catalogue of Life. Please refer to the original (or verbatim) taxonomic names for a more original view on the interaction data.

You can download the indexed dataset under review at [indexed-interactions.csv.gz](#). A tab-separated file can be found at [indexed-interactions.tsv.gz](#)

Figure 3: Interactions on taxonomic kingdom rank as interpreted by the Catalogue of Life download svg

Figure 4: Interactions on the taxonomic family rank as interpreted by the Catalogue of Life. [download svg](#)

Geospatial Distribution

If geospatial information was extracted from the dataset under review, the map below will show their distribution.

Hexagonal grid cells indicate that interactions claims are available for selected geospatial area: light yellow means relatively fewer claims, dark green relatively more claims.

Figure 5: Hexagonal grid cells indicate that interactions claims are available for selected geospatial area: light yellow means relatively fewer claims, dark green relatively more claims.

Associated data can be found in the geopackage files at indexed-interactions.gpkg for point data and indexed-interactions-h3.gpkg for data clustered in geospatial h3 hexagonals.

Learn more about the structure of this download at GloBI website, by opening a GitHub issue, or by sending an email.

Another way to discover the dataset under review is by searching for it on the GloBI website.

Taxonomic Alignment

As part of the review, all names are aligned against various name catalogs (e.g., col, ncbi, discoverlife, gbif, itis, wfo, mdd, tpt, pldb, and worms). These alignments can help review name usage or aid in selecting of a suitable taxonomic name resource.

Table 8: Sample of Name Alignments

providedName	relationName	resolvedCatalogName	resolvedName
Abax	HAS_ACCEPTED_NAME	col	Abax
Abax pallellopipedus	NONE	col	Abax pallellopipedus
Ablabesmyia	HAS_ACCEPTED_NAME	col	Ablabesmyia
Ablaxis	NONE	col	Ablaxis

Table 9: Distribution of Taxonomic Ranks of Aligned Names by Catalog. Names that were not aligned with a catalog are counted as NAs. So, the total number of unaligned names for a catalog will be listed in their NA row.

resolvedCatalogName	resolvedRank	count
col	NA	890
col	class	31

resolvedCatalogName	resolvedRank	count
col	family	218
col	genus	805
col	gigaclass	1
col	infraorder	2
col	kingdom	5
col	order	49
col	other	1
col	parvphylum	1
col	phylum	21
col	species	1992
col	subclass	5
col	subfamily	12
col	subgenus	40
col	suborder	6
col	subphylum	1
col	subspecies	23
col	superfamily	2
col	superorder	1
col	tribe	6
col	variety	2
discoverlife	NA	4048
discoverlife	species	2
gbif	NA	517
gbif	class	35
gbif	family	238
gbif	form	6
gbif	genus	918
gbif	kingdom	5
gbif	order	48
gbif	phylum	22
gbif	species	2294
gbif	subspecies	21
gbif	variety	12
itis	NA	1030
itis	class	29
itis	division	4
itis	family	223
itis	genus	770
itis	infraorder	2
itis	kingdom	5
itis	order	56
itis	phylum	23
itis	section	1
itis	species	1834

resolvedCatalogName	resolvedRank	count
itis	subclass	9
itis	subfamily	17
itis	subgenus	2
itis	suborder	13
itis	subphylum	6
itis	subspecies	17
itis	superclass	2
itis	superfamily	3
itis	superorder	2
itis	tribe	8
itis	variety	4
mdd	NA	4049
ncbi	NA	1024
ncbi	clade	7
ncbi	class	31
ncbi	cohort	1
ncbi	family	219
ncbi	genus	819
ncbi	infraorder	5
ncbi	kingdom	2
ncbi	order	51
ncbi	parvorder	2
ncbi	phylum	24
ncbi	series	1
ncbi	species	1823
ncbi	subclass	9
ncbi	subfamily	14
ncbi	subgenus	13
ncbi	suborder	7
ncbi	subphylum	2
ncbi	subspecies	7
ncbi	subtribe	1
ncbi	superclass	1
ncbi	superfamily	2
ncbi	superkingdom	1
ncbi	superorder	1
ncbi	tribe	6
pbdb	NA	2421
pbdb	class	34
pbdb	family	206
pbdb	genus	513
pbdb	informal	2
pbdb	infraclass	1
pbdb	infraorder	4

resolvedCatalogName	resolvedRank	count
pbdb	kingdom	4
pbdb	order	60
pbdb	phylum	25
pbdb	species	744
pbdb	subclass	7
pbdb	subfamily	17
pbdb	subkingdom	1
pbdb	suborder	11
pbdb	subphylum	3
pbdb	subspecies	1
pbdb	superclass	2
pbdb	superfamily	2
pbdb	superorder	1
pbdb	tribe	8
pbdb	unranked clade	20
tpt	NA	3231
tpt	family	42
tpt	genus	93
tpt	order	9
tpt	species	673
tpt	specific epithet	1
wfo	NA	3897
wfo	family	2
wfo	genus	73
wfo	phylum	1
wfo	species	76
wfo	subspecies	2
wfo	variety	1
worms	NA	2136
worms	class	30
worms	family	198
worms	forma	6
worms	genus	581
worms	gigaclass	1
worms	infraorder	3
worms	infraphylum	1
worms	kingdom	6
worms	order	53
worms	parvphylum	1
worms	phylum	22
worms	phylum (division)	4
worms	species	982
worms	subclass	9
worms	subfamily	6

resolvedCatalogName	resolvedRank	count
worms	subgenus	2
worms	suborder	8
worms	subphylum	5
worms	subspecies	3
worms	superclass	1
worms	superfamily	2
worms	superorder	1
worms	tribe	2
worms	variety	8

Table 10: Name relationship types per catalog. Name relationship type “NONE” means that a name was not recognized by the associated catalog. “SAME_AS” indicates either a “HAS_ACCEPTED_NAME” or “SYNONYM_OF” name relationship type. We recognize that “SYNONYM_OF” encompasses many types of nomenclatural synonymies (ICZN 1999) (e.g., junior synonym, senior synonyms).

resolvedCatalogName	relationName	count
col	HAS_ACCEPTED_NAME	3035
col	NONE	946
col	SYNONYM_OF	726
discoverlife	NONE	4235
discoverlife	HAS_ACCEPTED_NAME	2
gbif	HAS_ACCEPTED_NAME	3772
gbif	SYNONYM_OF	1372
gbif	NONE	565
itis	HAS_ACCEPTED_NAME	2836
itis	NONE	1076
itis	SYNONYM_OF	374
mdd	NONE	3818
mdd	HAS_ACCEPTED_NAME	385
mdd	SYNONYM_OF	3
ncbi	SAME_AS	2894
ncbi	NONE	1118
ncbi	SYNONYM_OF	273
ncbi	COMMON_NAME_OF	1
pbdb	HAS_ACCEPTED_NAME	1710
pbdb	NONE	2479
pbdb	SYNONYM_OF	232
tpt	NONE	3376
tpt	SYNONYM_OF	14

resolvedCatalogName	relationName	count
tpt	HAS_ACCEPTED_NAME	819
wfo	NONE	4050
wfo	SYNONYM_OF	45
wfo	HAS_ACCEPTED_NAME	122
wfo	HAS_UNCHECKED_NAME	15
worms	NONE	2188
worms	HAS_ACCEPTED_NAME	1878
worms	SYNONYM_OF	325

Table 11: List of Available Name Alignment Reports

catalog name	alignment results
col	associated names alignments report in gzipped html, csv, and tsv)
ncbi	associated names alignments report in gzipped html, csv, and tsv)
discoverlife	associated names alignments report in gzipped html, csv, and tsv)
gbif	associated names alignments report in gzipped html, csv, and tsv)
itis	associated names alignments report in gzipped html, csv, and tsv)
wfo	associated names alignments report in gzipped html, csv, and tsv)
mdd	associated names alignments report in gzipped html, csv, and tsv)
tpt	associated names alignments report in gzipped html, csv, and tsv)
pbdb	associated names alignments report in gzipped html, csv, and tsv)
worms	associated names alignments report in gzipped html, csv, and tsv)

Additional Reviews

Elton, Nomer, and other tools may have difficulties interpreting existing species interaction datasets. Or, they may misbehave, or otherwise show unexpected behavior. As part of the review process, detailed review notes are kept that document possibly misbehaving, or confused, review bots. An sample of review notes associated with this review can be found below.

Table 12: First few lines in the review notes.

reviewDate	reviewCommentType	reviewComment
2026-02-02T03:27:43Z	note	Unrecognized token 'org': was expecting (JSON String, Number, Array, Object or token 'null', 'true' or 'false') at [Source: (String)"org.eol.globi.domain.StudyImpl@60957c0f"; line: 1, column: 4]
2026-02-02T03:27:43Z	note	Unrecognized token 'org': was expecting (JSON String, Number, Array, Object or token 'null', 'true' or 'false') at [Source: (String)"org.eol.globi.domain.StudyImpl@53142455"; line: 1, column: 4]
2026-02-02T03:27:43Z	note	Unrecognized token 'org': was expecting (JSON String, Number, Array, Object or token 'null', 'true' or 'false') at [Source: (String)"org.eol.globi.domain.StudyImpl@40dff0b7"; line: 1, column: 4]
2026-02-02T03:27:43Z	note	Unrecognized token 'org': was expecting (JSON String, Number, Array, Object or token 'null', 'true' or 'false') at [Source: (String)"org.eol.globi.domain.StudyImpl@7966baa7"; line: 1, column: 4]

In addition, you can find the most frequently occurring notes in the table below.

Table 13: Most frequently occurring review notes, if any.

reviewComment	count
Unrecognized token 'org': was expecting (JSON String, Number, Array, Object or token 'null', 'true' or 'false') at [Source: (String)"org.eol.globi.domain.StudyImpl@60957c0f"; line: 1, column: 4]	1
Unrecognized token 'org': was expecting (JSON String, Number, Array, Object or token 'null', 'true' or 'false') at [Source: (String)"org.eol.globi.domain.StudyImpl@53142455"; line: 1, column: 4]	1
Unrecognized token 'org': was expecting (JSON String, Number, Array, Object or token 'null', 'true' or 'false') at [Source: (String)"org.eol.globi.domain.StudyImpl@40dff0b7"; line: 1, column: 4]	1
Unrecognized token 'org': was expecting (JSON String, Number, Array, Object or token 'null', 'true' or 'false') at [Source: (String)"org.eol.globi.domain.StudyImpl@7966baa7"; line: 1, column: 4]	1

For additional information on review notes, please have a look at the first 500 Review Notes in html format or the download full gzipped csv or tsv archives.

GloBI Review Badge

As part of the review, a review badge is generated. This review badge can be included in webpages to indicate the review status of the dataset under review.

Figure 6: Picture of a GloBI Review Badge ³

Note that if the badge is green, no review notes were generated. If the badge is yellow, the review bots may need some help with interpreting the species

³Up-to-date status of the GloBI Review Badge can be retrieved from the GloBI Review Depot

interaction data.

GloBI Index Badge

If the dataset under review has been registered with GloBI, and has been successfully indexed by GloBI, the GloBI Index Status Badge will turn green. This means that the dataset under review was indexed by GloBI and is available through GloBI services and derived data products.

Figure 7: Picture of a GloBI Index Badge ⁴

If you'd like to keep track of reviews or index status of the dataset under review, please visit GloBI's dataset index ⁵ for badge examples.

Discussion

This review and archive provides a means of creating citable versions of datasets that change frequently. This may be useful for dataset managers, including natural history collection data managers, as a backup archive of a shared Darwin Core archive. It also serves as a means of creating a trackable citation for the dataset in an automated way, while also including some information about the contents of the dataset.

This review aims to provide a perspective on the dataset to aid in understanding of species interaction claims discovered. However, it is important to note that this review does *not* assess the quality of the dataset. Instead, it serves as an indication of the open-ness⁶ and FAIRness (Wilkinson et al. 2016; Trekels et al. 2023) of the dataset: to perform this review, the data was likely openly available, **F**indable, **A**ccessible, **I**nteroperable and **R**eusable. The current Open-FAIR assessment is qualitative, and a more quantitative approach can be implemented with specified measurement units.

This report also showcases the reuse of machine-actionable (meta)data, something highly recommended by the FAIR Data Principles (Wilkinson et al. 2016). Making (meta)data machine-actionable enables more precise processing by computers, enabling even naive review bots like Nomer and Elton to interpret the data effectively. This capability is crucial for not just automating the generation of reports, but also for facilitating seamless data exchanges, promoting interoperability.

⁴Up-to-date status of the GloBI Index Badge can be retrieved from GloBI's API

⁵At time of writing (2026-02-02) the version of the GloBI dataset index was available at <https://globalbioticinteractions.org/datasets>

⁶According to <http://opendefinition.org/>: "Open data is data that can be freely used, reused and redistributed by anyone - subject only, at most, to the requirement to attribute and sharealike."

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Author contributions

Nomer was responsible for name alignments. Elton carried out dataset extraction, and generated the review notes. Preston tracked, versioned, and packaged, the dataset under review.

References

- Elliott, Michael, Jorrit Poelen, Icaro Alzuru, Emilio Berti, and partha04patel. 2025. “Bio-Guoda/Preston: 0.10.5.” Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14662206>.
- ICZN. 1999. “International Code of Zoological Nomenclature.” The International Trust for Zoological Nomenclature, London, UK. <https://www.iczn.org/the-code/the-code-online/>.
- Kuhn, Tobias, and Michel Dumontier. 2014. “Trusty URIs: Verifiable, Immutable, and Permanent Digital Artifacts for Linked Data.” In *The Semantic Web: Trends and Challenges*, edited by Valentina Presutti, Claudia d’Amato, Fabien Gandon, Mathieu d’Aquin, Steffen Staab, and Anna Tordai, 395–410. Cham: Springer International Publishing.
- Kuhn, Tobias, Jorrit Poelen, and Katrin Leinweber. 2025. “Globalbioticinteractions/Elton: 0.15.1.” Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14927734>.
- Poelen, Jorrit H. (ed.). 2024. “Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources Hash://Sha256/ B60c0d25a16ae77b24305782017b1a270b79b5d1746f832650 F2027ba536e276 Hash://Md5/17f1363a277ee0e4ecaf1b91c665e47e.” Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.12695629>.
- Poelen, Jorrit H., James D. Simons, and Chris J. Mungall. 2014. “Global Biotic Interactions: An Open Infrastructure to Share and Analyze Species-Interaction Datasets.” *Ecological Informatics* 24 (November): 148–59. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ecoinf.2014.08.005>.
- Poelen, Jorrit, Katja Seltmann, and Daniel Mietchen. 2024. “Globalbioticinteractions/Globinizer: 0.4.0.” Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10647565>.
- Salim, José Augusto, and Jorrit Poelen. 2025. “Globalbioticinteractions/Nomer: 0.5.15.” Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14893840>.
- Trekels, Maarten, Debora Pignatari Drucker, José Augusto Salim, Jeff Oller-ton, Jorrit Poelen, Filipi Miranda Soares, Max Rünzel, Muo Kasina,

- Quentin Groom, and Mariano Devoto. 2023. “WorldFAIR Project (D10.1) Agriculture-related pollinator data standards use cases report.” Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8176978>.
- Wilkinson, Mark D., Michel Dumontier, IJsbrand Jan Aalbersberg, Gabrielle Appleton, Myles Axton, Arie Baak, Niklas Blomberg, et al. 2016. “The FAIR Guiding Principles for Scientific Data Management and Stewardship.” *Scientific Data* 3 (1). <https://doi.org/10.1038/sdata.2016.18>.